

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 6.1

Horizon Europe Programme
HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No°101081883.

Start date of project: 1st December 2022

Duration: 48 months

D 6.1 - Initial Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

Deliverable details	
Work Package Title	WP6 – Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination
Task Number	T6.2 & T6.3
Deliverable Number	D6.1
Deliverable Title	Initial Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities
Revision Number	5
Responsible Organisation	MOVERIM
Author(s)	Laura Vivani
Due Date	Thursday, March 31, 2023
Delivered Date	Thursday, March 31, 2023
Reviewed by	Constantina Stavrou, Loucas Georgiou
Dissemination level	PU
Please cite as	Vivani L, D6.1 Initial Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities 2023, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu
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Initial Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

1. Content

1. Executive Summary.....	6
2. Introduction.....	7
2.1 Internal Survey D&E+C plan	8
3. Dissemination & Exploitation including Communication	10
3.1 Dissemination & Exploitation, including Communication goals	10
3.2 Target audience, stakeholders & channels	11
3.3 Baseline to design D&E+C materials	17
4. Project Branding.....	18
4.1 Visual identity guidelines.....	19
4.2 P2GreenN Logo	19
4.3 Presentation Template.....	20
5. Channels and Tools.....	21
5.1 Online Channels.....	21
5.1.1 P2GreenN Official website.....	21
5.1.2 P2GreenN's social media and online platforms	23
5.1.3 P2GreenN Newsletter.....	27
5.2.2 Press Releases	29
5.2.4 P2GreenN branded events and clustering activities	30
6. Evaluation.....	40
6.1 KPI & Targets.....	40
6.1 Reporting of D&E+C activities.....	43
7. Preliminary Exploitation Strategy.....	45
7.1 Key Exploitable results.....	45
7.2 Exploitation phases	47
8. Conclusions and Outlook.....	48
9. Annex	49

Index of figures

Figure 1: Introduction banner to the survey	8
Figure 2: Role in the project and organisation represented	9
Figure 3: The official logo of the project to be used in all context	19
Figure 4: P2GreenN Presentation template	19

Figure 5: Main channels partners use to communicate	20
Figure 6: P2GreenN's website homepage	21
Figure 7: Availability to publish P2GreenN's articles on partners' websites	22
Figure 8 Availability to share P2GreenN's content on personal accounts	25
Figure 9: Dissemination Table Dashboard	42
Figure 10: Exploitation Calendar	46
Figure 11 : Overview about workshops, events and interviews planned by P2GreenN in a timely order. Synergies of events are shown and the size of audience and structure, project meetings are included.	48

Index of tables

Table 1: Target audience Table with Communication and Dissemination (D&E+C) tools and channels	12
Table 2: Examples of networks in which partners are involved	15
Table 3: Baseline messages	17
Table 4: Materials included in the D&E+C Kit	28
Table 5: Projects which could cluster with P2GreenN	36
Table 6: Key events to be attended by P2GreenN's partners	39
Table 7: Dissemination KPIs	40
Table 8: D&E+C Activity and KPIs summarised	41
Table 9 Summary of anticipated KERs	44

1. Executive Summary

This document outlines the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication (D&E+C) strategy of P2Green and the related planned activities carried out within Work Package 6 "Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination".

As outlined by Project Officer Sofia Pachini, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication are key assets for P2Green for the following reasons.

Disseminate is to make the project results public for others to use. This activity targets not only scientists but also authorities, industry and social society. That's why dissemination is crucial to maximize the impact of the project's outcomes. Therefore, the activity will be carried out throughout the entire duration of the project, as soon as the action has results.

Exploitation implies making concrete use of the results for commercial, societal and political purposes. This pivotal activity targets the industry (SMEs included) and all those who can make good use of the project's results. Exploitation's ultimate goals are the production of new legislative outputs or recommendations and the creation of benefits for innovation, the economy and society.

Communication is key to inform, promote and communicate the project's activities and results to citizens, the media and stakeholders. This ensures the exchange of information and engagement with stakeholders and the disclosure of the project's achievements in a targeted manner, also showing the success of European collaboration.

Throughout the project, the consortium will communicate and promote P2Green, raising awareness among relevant stakeholders potentially interested in its research results and improved methodologies.

Partners will also collaborate to empower and engage project participants (e.g., agricultural experts, cities, water services companies, etc.) to ensure a clear understanding of the project domain context, objectives, and expected outcomes. Furthermore, the consortium will cluster actions with other national, European, and international projects and R&D and EU initiatives like P2Green. P2Green will also foster engagement and collaboration with other networks and initiatives devoted to the circular transition, such as the Circular Cities Declaration and the European Commission-led Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI). P2Green will also interact with other significant EU Projects. Indeed, P2Green will treasure the experience built by other partnerships in previous research projects, taking inspiration from the European Commission's Research and Innovation success stories portal. The networking activity aims to share knowledge and good practice, create interactions and discussion opportunities, take advantage of other field experiences, and build a stakeholder network.

In general, D&E+C activities will support all the WPs. More specifically, WP6 will assist WP3 in involving farmers and other relevant stakeholders in Task 3.3 "Awareness-raising & enhancing social acceptance" to increase the societal acceptance of P2Green's innovative solutions. Furthermore, WP4 will also receive support from WP6 in actively engaging with target groups, such as policymakers, through bilateral meetings with the goal of sharing ideas, reporting on activities and presenting the project's recommendations for European practices.

Regarding stakeholders' engagement activities, WP6 will work closely with WP5. Where needed, WP6 will support Task 5.5 "Develop synergies and collaboration with Horizon Europe clusters 1-5 and projects, cities & regions across the EU" to encourage a multilateral exchange of information with relevant stakeholders and other EU-funded projects through the participation in roundtables, open days, action groups, individual contacts, etc.

Further, WP1 and WP5 will be supported by specific campaigns on social networks and local media in the following languages: German, Swedish and Spanish, Greek, Italian, French and Hungarian. D&E+C actions will be intensified after conducting the stakeholder mapping and socio-cultural analysis in the pilot regions (Sweden, Germany, Spain) and the follower regions (Greece, Italy, France, and Hungary).

The Initial plan for the dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities, provides a list of activities and an outreach strategy. In addition, it encompasses two features:

- Shared strategy: WP6 has launched an internal survey to assess the preferences and communication capabilities of the consortium. Starting from this knowledge baseline, the Plan has been drafted to enhance the outreach strategy effectiveness and ensure smooth coordination among the consortia.
- Dynamic approach: The first version of the Plan will be periodically updated to follow the project's progression. Moreover, D&E+C tools will be designed to be modular to fit different D&E+C channels and leverage partners' ongoing activities. This dynamic approach will ensure that planned activities are aligned with the project's outputs, delivering the message to the target audience when needed.

Throughout the project, the effectiveness of D&E+C initiatives will be assessed using an ad-hoc monitoring system. The Plan describes the tools and key performance indicators that will be adopted.

2. Introduction

This Initial Plan for the dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities, sets the D&E+C framework for P2Green and serves as a guide for all dissemination & exploitation, and communication activities throughout the project's lifetime. This is a working document since it reflects the partner's ongoing activities and will be updated following the project's progression (every year).

The plan will serve as a guide to:

1. Identify/update specific communication objectives.
2. Understand the target audience.
3. Develop messaging strategies.
4. Select appropriate channels/tools.
5. Disseminate messages through proper channels.
6. Conduct systematic research to inform and evaluate communication activities.

It will also establish a link with the partner's expertise and ongoing activities. This information has been collected through an internal survey launched by WP6 co-leader, Moverim. Each section of the document will have a brief overview of the survey's results and explain how partners' contributions have been integrated into the Plan.

The Plan is not strictly divided between a dissemination, exploitation, and communication part, as most tools and channels used for dissemination serve exploitation and communication purposes, too. For example, social media will be used to disseminate and communicate about the project and to facilitate the exploitation of project results. According to this logic, activities and content will be developed, making them modular to fit different D&E+C channels and to leverage partners' ongoing activities. The only differentiation between D&E+C will be made at the level of general objectives. Moreover, an explanation of the importance of results' exploitation and of the procedures to monitor exploitable results are included in this document.

2.1 Internal Survey D&E+C plan

As mentioned above, Moverim has launched an internal survey to assess the D&E+C needs and capabilities of the consortium. With 32 partners, P2Green involves organisations linked to different target audiences (see Figure 1): from research institutions to SMEs, from consulting companies to non-profits, the consortium has the potential to reach an extremely wide audience. Starting from these links, the approach aims to develop an adaptive plan that leverages the partner's expertise and its ongoing activities to maximise the project's overall impact. Moreover, it ensures that D&E+C activities are aligned with the preferences of P2Green's consortium, improving the coordination among partners. All the data have been shared with the other WPs.

Figure 1: Introduction banner to the survey

The form has been organized into four sections:

1. Partner identification: to identify the respondent's role in the project and its institution/organisation. The first section has been adopted to personalize the questionnaire, delivering a set of targeted questions aligned with the respondent's role. Participants were asked to answer just the questions inherent to their field of activities to complete and collect relevant information for the Plan. This methodological choice ensures the collection of data tailored to the roles and responsibilities of partners and, as a further positive outcome, it allows the consortium to quickly complete the questionnaire not having to answer to questions unrelated to their specific tasks.

2. Stakeholder and cluster activities: to assess which projects and initiatives the respondents (or their institution/organisation) are involved in, focusing on the ones inherent to P2GreeN's. The goal was to draft a first list of projects and initiatives with potential interest in developing synergies with P2GreeN. This list will also serve as a platform to recruit participants for the project's activities and identify target stakeholder groups, the information will be shared with WP5.

3. Web and social network: to collect respondents' preferences on digital content and assess their availability to contribute to D&E+C activities, including sharing P2GreeN content on their accounts or through the online channels of their institutions. The information collected in this section will drive the online strategy of the project. Digital content will be designed to reflect the insights collected and gathered from the consortium: leveraging the respondents' expertise, WP6 will develop and share messages that are relevant to the target audience

4. Dissemination of results: to collect information about the dissemination of scientific results from the researchers involved in the project. Respondents were asked to provide details about planned publications, scientific journals, conferences, and events' organisation. The data collected will support the planning of dissemination activities and provide insights to design the monitoring strategy.

Overall, (at the time of this deliverable) the survey has collected responses from 29 partners involved in P2GreeN, achieving a nearly complete representation of the consortium. As shown in Figure 2, most respondents are Project Managers (60%), followed by Researchers (28.6%). Principal investigators represent 11.4% of the sample.

Most of the P2GreenN consortium come from companies or SMEs (45.7%), followed by research institutions (22.9%), Universities (17.1%) and “others” (associations, cities, non-profits etc.) which represent 14.3% of the responses (See figure 2).

Figure 2: Role in the project and organisation represented

3. Dissemination & Exploitation including Communication

3.1 *Dissemination & Exploitation, including Communication goals*

Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication activities will ensure a successful diffusion of P2GreenN outcomes to all stakeholders within and beyond the consortium. It is a transversal action in which all partners will be involved to maximise the reach of the project and its empowering aims. The Dissemination & Exploitation, including Communication Plan (D&E+C Plan) will design and coordinate these activities to achieve several goals.

In terms of **dissemination**, the Plan will:

- Support sustainable food systems from fork to farm offering viable alternatives to reduce the current usage of mineral fertilisers;
- Reach out to relevant stakeholders to provide a consistent, accessible and practical information base.
- Propose innovative green bio-based fertilisers and thus minimise the pressure on the natural resources, specifically water and soil;
- Foster a circular material flow system between urban and rural areas, thereby restoring the coupling of the water-agri-food system following the 3R principle “Reduce, Reuse, Recover”;
- Support innovative governance solutions;
- Turn the project results into empowering tools applicable in a real setting;
- Educate the target audience and inform policymakers about P2GreenN's research topics and methodologies.

In terms of **exploitation**, the Plan will:

- Foster innovation in the field of bio-based fertilisers
- Develop innovative N and P recovery solutions for the utilization of human sanitary waste from urban settlements and its conversion into safe bio-based fertilisers for agricultural production;
- Create solutions for the circular economy to halt and eliminate nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution by connecting blue urban with green rural infrastructure;
- Suggest innovative governance developments from both a legal and an urban planning perspective, hopefully leading to new legislation and policy recommendations;
- Turn the project results into empowering tools applicable in real settings beyond the project's areas of intervention.

In terms of **communication**, the Plan will:

- Spread the results of P2GreeN using an innovative approach to empower European stakeholders, lead users, and corresponding institutions beyond Europe;
- Raise social acceptance for human extraction in fertilisation in the agri-food production and develop methods and tools to increase societal awareness of P2GreeN's groundbreaking innovations and their positive outcomes.
- Raise awareness about P2GreeN's innovative technology to support sustainable food systems from fork to farm, offering viable alternatives to reduce the current usage of mineral fertilisers;
- Inform practitioners on the relevance of innovative green bio-based fertilisers and how they can minimise the pressure on natural resources, ultimately enhancing environmental preservation.

As previously mentioned, the Plan will design activities to accomplish dissemination, exploitation, and communication goals. The idea is to develop a modular set of activities that adapt to the project's progress over time.

Also, communication in its multiple channels (website, social pages...) will have a key and synergistic role in sensitising the targets (and the population in general) and in supporting literacy and empowerment activities.

3.2 Target audience, stakeholders & channels

Many actors potentially interested in the project's concepts, objectives, approaches, activities, and future results have been identified. They are presented in Table 1 along with D&E+C tools, channels, and the partners involved in the activities. Each tool and channel will be described further in this document, also in accordance with the content of Deliverable 6.3 which deepens the project's visual identity and some communication channels.

Certain communication activities will target the general audience indiscriminately. That's the case for informative material about the project's background shared through non-scientific articles, social media, and public events. Other tools will be directed towards specific groups, such as experts in agriculture (i.e., farmers, researchers, agricultural engineers etc.), water associations, water services providers, sanitation providers, fertiliser producers, relevant stakeholders and institutions, and local and regional authorities. For each target group the knowledge level, ambitions, needs, scientific knowledge, and experience in the field will be considered to design a tailored strategy.

In general, the project will highlight the link to Horizon Europe and display the EU Emblem. This will increase public awareness about the role of the EU in supporting research developments in the field of bio-based fertilisers while also enhancing knowledge on how public money is spent for the benefit of society.

Target audience		D&E+C Tools and Channels	
General Public		Online	Infographics and short videos on P2Green website and social media
		Offline	Poster, leaflets, brochures, and presentations
Experts in agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agricultural economists ● Agricultural scientists ● Agricultural engineers ● Farmers ● Researchers 	Online	Blog articles, infographics and short videos on P2Green website, social media and newsletters
		Offline	Scientific publications, press releases, poster, leaflets, brochures, presentations in conferences, events and fairs
Agricultural organisations, environmental agency and water association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● COPA-COGECA, ● Farm Europe ● CEJA the European Council of Young Farmers ● IFOAM ● European Environment Agency ● EurEau 	Online	Blog articles and short videos on the P2Green website, social media, and newsletters
		Offline	Press releases, poster, leaflets, brochures, presentations in conferences, fairs and clustering events
Policy makers and regional/national authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EU policy-makers ● Ministries of Agriculture and Food in partner's countries ● Regional and local agricultural authorities ● Regional and local water treatment/management authorities ● Planning departments in cities across Europe 	Online	Blog articles, infographics and short videos on the P2Green website, social media and newsletters
		Offline	Press releases, poster, leaflets, brochures, presentations in conferences, fairs and clustering events
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sanitation ● Fertiliser producers ● Water services providers ● Water treatment providers ● Public utility companies 	Online	Articles on specialised websites
		Offline	Press releases and promotion at conferences and trade fairs
Media and General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-specialised media ● Citizens 	Online	Blog articles and infographics on the P2Green website and social media

		Offline	Press releases, printed articles poster, leaflets, brochures, and presentation in large events
Other EU projects and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Projects/Initiatives related to P2GREEN's research topics, working in synergy with WP5 	Online	Blog articles and Infographics on the P2Green website and social media
		Offline	Press releases, printed articles, poster, leaflets, brochures, and presentations in clustering events.

Table 1: Target audience Table with Communication and Dissemination (D&E+C) tools and channels

As emerged from the Internal Survey, almost half of the respondents (41%) are involved, personally or through their organisation, in national/international networks relevant to the P2Green project. An overview of these networks is shown in Table 2.

Network name	Description	URL
ICLEI	ICLEI is a network of local and regional authorities committed to sustainability.	link
Circular Cities Declaration (CCD)	The Circular Cities Declaration is a commitment document from cities and regions to use the levers at their disposal coherently across the organisation to transition from a linear to a circular economy.	link
Covenant of Mayors	The EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy brings together thousands of local governments that want to secure a better future for their citizens. By joining the initiative, they voluntarily commit to implementing EU climate and energy objectives.	link
Water Europe	Water Europe (WE) is the voice and promoter of water-related innovation and RTD in Europe.	link
International Water Association	The International Water Association is the network of water professionals striving for a world in which water is wisely, sustainably, and equitably managed.	link
Sustainable Sanitation Alliance	The Sustainable Sanitation Alliance (SuSanA) is an informal network of organisations with a common vision on sustainable sanitation.	link

IWA Resource-Oriented Sanitation Cluster	The cluster's IWA Specialist Groups work on specific topics or in well-defined areas, sharing in-depth knowledge among group members on that topic.	link
Future Earth Ireland committee	Future Earth Ireland is the national adhering committee for Future Earth Global and is facilitated by the Royal Irish Academy.	link
EurAgEng	The European Society of Agricultural Engineers (EurAgEng) exists to promote the profession of Agricultural and Biosystems.	link
HellaBiom	HellaBiom promotes sustainable biomass valorisation to benefit the local communities, the environment and the economy.	link
HelAgEng	Hellenic Association of Agricultural Engineers	link
BioRural	BioRural seeks to promote currently available small-scale bio-based solutions with a view to strengthening Bioeconomy in European rural areas.	link
CLEVER Cities	CLEVER Cities project aims to drive a new kind of nature-based urban transformation for sustainable and socially inclusive cities across Europe, Latin America and China.	link
KOPOS	KOPOS addresses the question of how greater regionalisation of food supply can contribute to building environmentally friendly and more resilient supply structures	link
Andalusian Network Against Climate Change (REDAC)	It is an open, participative space aimed at promoting social awareness about the problem of climate change.	link
EIT Food	EIT Food accelerates innovation to build a future-fit food system that produces healthy and sustainable food for all.	link
Inter-Platform Circular Economy Group	The group has the aim of encouraging public-private collaboration in the field of research and innovation, and circular economy.	link
World Alliance for Efficient Solutions by SOLAR IMPULSE FOUNDATION	World Alliance brings together the main actors in the field of clean technologies.	link
European Circular Economy Stakeholders Platform	As a joint initiative by the European Commission and the European Economic and Social Committee, the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform brings together stakeholders active in the broad field of the circular economy in Europe.	link
Circular Economy Industry Platform	The platform is a web tool managed by BusinessEurope and its national members that contributes to the EU's agenda on circular economy.	link

European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform	ESPP brings together companies, scientists and stakeholders for sustainable phosphorus management and nutrient recycling.	link
WATER ACTION HUB	The Water Action Hub raises awareness, catalyses collaboration, and scales critical lessons on water sustainability and climate resilience around the world.	link
C40 Cities	C40 Cities is a global network of mayors taking urgent action to confront the climate crisis and create a future where everyone can thrive.	link
EJPSoil	The overall goal of the EJP SOIL programme is to build a sustainable European integrated research system and develop and deploy a reference framework on climate-smart, sustainable agricultural soil management.	link
ADEME	ADEME's mission is to accelerate the transition to a more sober and supportive, job-generating, humane and harmonious society.	link
LEX4BIO	The project aims to optimise the usage of bio-based fertilisers by collecting and processing regional nutrient stock, flow, surplus and deficiency data, and reviewing and assessing the required technological solutions.	link
ARCEAU Ile-de-France Association	Working group of the ARCEAU Ile-de-France Association on source separation of domestic wastewater	link
NetSan e.V.	NetSan e.V. is a network of different actors working together for the sanitation and nutrient transition.	link
Local IPCC (le "GREC francilien")	Group of researchers dedicated to helping regional institutions to fulfill ecological transition.	link
European Regional Science Association (ERSA)	The European Regional Science Association (ERSA) is the supranational grouping of national regional science associations across Europe.	link
Regional Studies Association (RSA)	The Regional Studies Association is an academic society concerned with the analysis of regions and regional issues.	link
Hungarian Regional Science Association (MRTT)	The Association provides a professional forum for regional scholars and practitioners and serves as a bridge between international and Hungarian regional scientists by getting connected with international regional science organisations.	link
Hellenic Fertilizer' Association (S.P.E.L)	The Hellenic Fertilizer' Association focuses its attention on the promotion of the efficient and responsible use of fertilisers for plant growth, respecting the environment.	link
EIP-AGRI network	An EU-wide EIP-AGRI network is being built to support EIP-AGRI activities through	link

	communication, partnering, dissemination, knowledge flows and collecting practice needs for future projects and programming. The network activities are facilitated by a professional team of experts at the EIP-AGRI Service Point established in Brussels.	
Leibniz Association	The Leibniz Association connects 97 independent research institutions that range in focus from natural, engineering, and environmental sciences to economics, spatial and social sciences, and the humanities.	link
Agricultural Systems of the Future	Consortium with eight German BMBF-funded projects demonstrating innovative approaches for the sustainable design of future agricultural production.	link
zirkulierBAR – REGION.innovativ	German BMBF-funded project that demonstrates a sustainable regional circular economy by recovering nutrients from consumed food and returning them to agriculture.. The project has a wide network of national and international stakeholders.	link
Innosuisse	Innosuisse is the Swiss Innovation Agency. Its role is to promote science-based innovation in the interest of the economy and society in Switzerland	link
Artes – group	Developing and building sustainable and durable works of art.	link

Table 2: Examples of networks in which partners are involved

The database shown in Table 2 will be constantly updated and expanded, leveraging links and connections between project partners and their stakeholders. This activity will be carried out together with WP5.

Partners will be asked to provide further information about stakeholders and networks in a dedicated form shared in the project’s MS Teams channel. Thus, WP6 will actively contribute to T5.1 (“Development of a P2GreenN network hub for engagement, outreach and impact”) by providing suggestions for stakeholders.

Additional contacts may be captured through stakeholder’s registration at P2GreenN’s events if they have provided permission to be contacted in the future. All contacts will be stored in the inventory to be used for disseminating updates, results, and outcomes and for issuing invitations to relevant events. The inventory and registration form will be amalgamated and regularly cleansed to remove redundancy and repetition.

Accordingly, personal data will not be made public or shared with a third party without the individual's expressed consent. Further information will be provided in D7.3 "Initial data management plan".

3.3 **Baseline to design D&E+C materials**

To optimise the impact of the outreach effort, D&E+C materials will be developed starting from a common baseline defined for each target group. Depending on the audience, the baseline will serve as a guide to remind the partners which message they should highlight in D&E+C materials. Table 3 presents the baseline for each target audience and will be updated during the project's lifetime according to the project's progress.

The baselines will be divided into two categories:

- The first category, "**If they join P2Green**", refers to the promotional campaign the consortium will adopt to onboard participants in project activities. The idea is to incentivise the public, professionals and researchers to join project activities by highlighting what they can get from P2Green.
- The second category, "**If they follow P2Green's channels**" relates to the promotional activities that partners will implement to raise awareness about the project. The idea is to incentivise the public, experts, and researchers to follow the project's channels to learn more about P2Green's innovation topics.

Target audience	Baseline (What do they get from P2Green?)	
Farmers, water management	If they join P2Green	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefit from the empowerment activities.
	If they follow P2Green's channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to project's outcomes and contents. • Access to P2Green's empowerment toolbox, facilitating their acquisition, comprehension and learning of the benefit of sustainable approaches to nutrient recovery from sanitary waste.
Experts in agriculture	If they join P2Green	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to project data through the innovation platform • Better interaction with other professionals, even outside the project and from other disciplines.

	If they follow P2Green's channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to project's outcomes and scientific publications. • Practical solutions advice to empower farmers.
Agricultural organisations, environmental agency and water association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates about the different stages of the project. • Opportunity to provide feedback on the project's objectives, activities, and results. • New technologies to convert human sanitary waste into bio-based fertilizers. • New viable and sustainable approaches to nutrient recovery from sanitary waste. • Opportunity to start collaborations to foster exploitation. 	
Policy makers and regional/national authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New agriculture and sustainable sanitation models are at their disposal, to be used in their own countries to reduce costs derived by the activation of these innovative services. • New technology and frameworks to use the considerable amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus generated daily by human sanitary waste in cities or urban areas to convert it into bio-based fertilisers. • New viable and sustainable approaches to nutrient recovery from sanitary waste. 	
Industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates about the different stages of the project. • Opportunity to provide feedback on the project's objectives, activities, and results. • Opportunity to start collaborations for the exploitation of P2Green's outputs. • Opportunity to build on P2Green's results to spread its innovative outcomes even further 	
Media and General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A better understanding of sustainable approaches to nutrient recovery from sanitary waste. • A better understanding of the P and N's impact on the environment and of the positive outcomes of the 3R in terms of saving energy and natural resources. • Awareness about innovative agricultural and sustainable sanitation. • Better understanding of how Europe is working towards a greener future. 	

Table 3: Baseline messages

4. Project Branding

A defined **colour palette has been decided**, a **project logo**, and a **template** (PowerPoint) are to be adopted by the P2Green partners for all D&E+C activities, both internal and external ones.

The material above mentioned is extensively explained in D6.3.

A solid and dynamic visual identity is essential in many ways, to:

- Provide an easily identifiable and attractive design to facilitate dialogue and recognition with key stakeholders and influencers.
- Give a brand platform for improved market knowledge of P2Green's solutions to support replication and take-up.
- Enhance the exploitation potential of research, business models and innovations.

Support collaboration activities with relevant projects and initiatives at a local, national, and European level

4.1 Visual identity guidelines

Key to the success of P2Green's visual identity will be the consortium's proper use of its visual elements and tools. **Visual identity guidelines** have been set up to support partners in effectively showcasing and promoting P2Green's image (D 6.3).

The image user guide includes information about the Logo and its usage, the colour palette, the fonts and how to correctly acknowledge the European Commission's support. The guidelines have been published on the project's MS Teams channel: partners can download the guidelines along with templates and the P2Green's Logo.

4.2 P2Green Logo

A logo has been designed to give a striking and easy-to-recognise visual identity to the project. The logo must not be altered or adapted by project partners but used in its current form (See figure 3). Care must be taken not to distort the dimensions of the logo as well. Different versions (coloured, black & white) are available (detailed information in D6.3).

Figure 3: The official logo of the project to be used in all context

4.3 Presentation Template

The PowerPoint template (Figure 4) ensures that communication from partners is aligned with the common visual identity. The consistent visual and written style will provide project recognition and deliver a unified identity, especially when partners present P2Green at events, conferences, and fairs. The template has been distributed to project partners and is available on the P2Green's MS Teams channel. (See D 6.3).

Figure 4: P2Green Presentation template

5. Channels and Tools

P2GreenN will reach target groups with a Channel Mix strategy. Communication and dissemination activities will be delivered in both forms, **online and offline**.

The Plan provides a brief description of the different online and offline channels and identifies the contents they will host. Channel and content have been selected with the support of the project's partners, leveraging the insights from the Internal Survey.

5.1 Online Channels

P2GreenN online communication will rely on three channels: the project's official website, social networks, and newsletters. These are also the three main channels that partner organisations use to communicate their routine activities. Hence, the project's digital content will be shared twice, leveraging the partner's official channels to attract new visitors.

Figure 5: Main channels partners use to communicate

5.1.1 P2GreenN Official website

As appointed in D6.3 the project website (<https://p2green.eu>) provides all relevant information about the project: objectives, target groups, information of the participating partners, events timeline, and latest activities news.

Figure 6: P2Green's website homepage

Portal features:

- **Landing page:** A general overview of the project which briefly describes P2Green's objectives, project's work-plan and partners.
- **About the project:** Detailed overview of the project.
- **Work Packages:** Detailed description of the project.
- **Events:** Section showcasing the projects events.
- **Contact us page**
- **News:** A collection of articles, updates, and news about the project.

The website will host different kinds of digital content in the News section. WP6 leaders will develop the content in collaboration with the consortium. P2Green's contents will focus on four main categories (listed in order of priority):

1. Blog posts on background information: concerning the innovative scientific ideas and future business models and governance solutions underpinning the P2Green project. These articles are designed to explain the project in a simple and accessible way. All the partners will contribute by writing some of these articles.
2. Blog posts to present partners: almost 80% of the partners involved in the Internal Survey declared to be available for a short interview or presentation. WP6 leaders will publish a blog post on the topic. Each interviewee will present the partner and describe their role in the project as well as the benefit of P2Green's scientific, business, governance and societal implications.
3. News to present publications: this content will announce new scientific articles from partners working on P2Green. The news will briefly present the article, explain who the authors are and provide a link to access it on the knowledge hub of the website.

4. News from the EU Commission: the EU Commission organises several events related to P2Green's topics. The idea is to present these initiatives and deliver the key messages from the Commission's event, highlighting how P2Green is contributing to EU strategic priorities.

Besides the four categories of digital content, MOVERIM and CIP will regularly publish blog posts to announce P2Green's events and the participation of partners in scientific conferences. Follow-up articles will summarise the content of the events with key messages from the main speakers and pictures.

Most project managers involved in the Internal survey declared that it is possible to share P2Green's articles on the news section of their organisations' websites (See Figure 7). Hence, when possible, P2Green will leverage partners' websites to increase the outreach of the project's online portal. Having links from distinguished websites leading to www.p2green.eu will improve P2Green's website ranking in SEO (Search Engine Optimization) and ultimately its visibility.

IS IT POSSIBLE TO SHARE P2GREEN'S ARTICLES (NEWS, EVENTS, INTERVIEWS, ETC.) ON THE NEWS SECTION OF YOUR ORGANISATION'S WEBSITE?

Figure 7: Availability to publish P2Green's articles on partners' websites

5.1.2 P2Green's social media and online platforms

P2Green's social media will be strategic to achieve D&E+C objectives. As stated in D6.3 are being managed by CIP (Citizens in Power) in conjunction with MOVERIM. Social media are valuable tools to connect with professionals, policymakers, academics, and citizens. They also serve as a platform to keep the community engaged and expand the project's audience.

The project has officially launched on the following platforms: **Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram** and **YouTube**.

Twitter is a valuable platform for users to follow the project's progression and related events in real-time. Moreover, it can be adopted as a tool to monitor posts and comments about P2Green's research topics. The communication team will **enlarge the Twitter community** by searching for accounts pinpointed in the stakeholder list as followers. All relevant European bodies and P2Green partners will be followed as well. Once the starter community has been settled, the team will establish more connections with accounts related to the project. An **analysis** will be carried out to identify a repertoire of unbranded hashtags to attract followers, give tweets more visibility and help reach a broad audience (e.g., #SustainableSanitation, #weareREAdy and more generic hashtags such as #CircularEconomy #EUfunding). Reference to relevant external social accounts will be used to issue selected tweets for retweets. Relevant posts by scientific journals/organisations'/other projects' accounts will also be reposted.

LinkedIn will be used to host a 'company page' in the professional domain. P2Green will develop a **LinkedIn community** by inviting project partners to follow the page and sending private messages to target stakeholders. Connections with other relevant initiatives in the field and links with EU institutions will further enlarge P2Green 's community on LinkedIn. LinkedIn will help to establish P2Green as a standout initiative in the field, make its name known and create a network of stakeholders that could be interested in its research domain. Connection with Agriculture professionals, Water management services, the Sanitation industry, and Farmers will also foster the exploitation of P2Green 's innovative outputs.

Facebook will be adopted to engage with non-scientific stakeholders. P2Green activity on Facebook will focus on municipalities and citizens. The communication team will leverage Facebook powerful advertising tools to onboard communities and farmers in the project activities. Target ads will promote the project, highlighting the benefits of joining P2Green's community. Facebook will also serve as a channel for empowerment activities to foster the acquisition, comprehension and learning of information from the general public.

Instagram and YouTube will be adopted to share graphics and video contents about the project.

The communication team will share through **Instagram** infographics and pictures from past events. It will also promote content from the P2GreeN website, inviting users to visit its online portal. Each post will feature an image and a brief abstract to provide a visual and textual explanation of the content.

P2GreeN's **YouTube** channel will include short informative videos to explain the scientific background of the project. The communication team will also upload video interviews with partners and locals from the pilot regions involved in the project's activities. Additionally, users will find the recording from past events organised by P2GreeN. If available, the channel will also include video of partners presenting the project at external events.

P2GreeN's social media will host various kinds of **digital content** adapted to the platform and the target audience. The WP6 leaders will develop the content in collaboration with the consortium. As suggested by partners in the Internal survey P2GreeN 's social content will focus on four main categories (listed in order of priority):

1. **Short informative videos:** including videos from P2GreeN events, videos from partner's presentations at conferences, textual video to explain the project's background, videos about project's updates and activities. Each video will have a short duration to keep viewers engaged (between 1 to 3 minutes). It will also feature subtitles to allow users to watch the video without the sound.
2. **Infographics:** visually appealing infographics will be shared through social media to explain the project's background. The goal is to attract user attention and deliver relevant information concerning Sustainable Sanitation, Agricultural innovation, and sustainable food systems from fork to farm etc. Adopting graphical content will increase the chance that other accounts re-share P2GreeN's posts, especially if the infographic explains topics of general interest.
3. **News related to the project's research topics:** WP6 leaders will monitor different sources to identify P2GreeN research topics. Other domains will be observed, including policy, science, and industry. Relevant news will be shared through P2GreeN's social media accounts, along with a cover picture and a brief description to explain how the information is linked to the project (see Figure 11).
4. **Short video interviews:** with professionals and researchers. The idea is to produce short videos in which P2GreeN's researchers and participants explain the project from different perspectives. Interviews with researchers, for

example, will focus on P2GreeN's innovative approach to agriculture, sustainable sanitation, and green transition.

5. **Post to present scientific publication:** When a partner publishes a scientific article related to P2GreeN, WP6 leaders will announce it on social media. The post will briefly present the article, giving information about the writers and why the paper is important for the project.

To increase the outreach of P2GreeN social media content, partners will be asked to re-share the post from the project on their official pages. The partners will also be involved by re-sharing the P2GreeN contents on their personal accounts: more than 85% of respondents in the Internal Survey declared to be open to sharing P2GreeN's contents on their personal accounts (see Figure 8). Where possible, P2GreeN's post will directly tag individuals related to P2GreeN's activities. This strategy should improve the performance of the posts, leading new visitors to follow P2GreeN.

To better clarify social media contribution, WP6 leaders prepared a Social Media guideline, which was already shared in P2GreeN's MS Teams channel with all partners.

WOULD YOU BE OPEN TO SHARE ON YOUR PERSONAL LINKEDIN AND TWITTER ACCOUNTS CONTENTS RELATED TO THE PROJECT?

Figure 8 Availability to share P2GreeN's content on personal accounts

To foster the outreach of scientific publications and project's public deliverables, P2GreeN will leverage the following online platforms: **ResearchGate, Zenodo and EOSC Portal**.

Partners will be asked to share research papers derived from P2GreeN through their personal **ResearchGate** accounts. As emerged from the Internal Survey, 50% of the researchers have a ResearchGate account and can share the publications from the project. This approach should foster the dissemination of project's results, especially among the scientific community. Moreover, considering that papers will include acknowledgement of funding from Horizon Europe, sharing the publication on ResearchGate will raise awareness about the EU effort toward research and innovation.

A project **Zenodo** account will be set up to upload peer-reviewed publications, posters, press releases, newsletters, policy briefs, and other documents and media. The P2Green Zenodo account will host this content beyond the lifespan of the projects. Moreover, when uploading any documents or media, partners will have the option to link them to other relevant communities. It is envisaged that this will enhance impact by sharing expertise across disciplines and topic areas, such as approaches toward agricultural and farming innovation, water management and sustainable sanitation

The **EOSC Portal** <https://eosc-portal.eu/> is one of the expected core services contributing to the implementation of the "Access and interface" action line on the EOSC roadmap. It was designed to provide a European delivery channel connecting the EOSC's demand and supply sides, as well as all its stakeholders. The EOSC Portal is a gateway to information and resources in EOSC, providing updates on its governance and players and the projects contributing to its realisation.

P2Green – as suggested by project officer Sofia Pachini – will strategically take advantage of the following **European Commission's Tools**:

- Horizon Result Platform
- Research and Innovation success stories
- Horizon Dashboard
- Horizon Results Booster
- Innovation Radar
- Horizon Magazine
- Horizon Impact Award

5.1.3 P2Green Newsletter

WP6 leaders will prepare periodic Newsletters to report on the project's latest developments, summarise the main achievements, and address the most relevant activities for the following periods. It will be shared internally to inform individuals within partner organisations and externally to promote the project among stakeholders. The Newsletter will include the following contents:

- Edited versions of project press releases.
- Announcements of progress by specific partners or WPs.
- Reports on conferences and meetings where P2Green is involved.
- News on Milestone achievements.
- Information about forthcoming events.
-

A **template** for the Newsletter will be prepared at the beginning of the project and shared with the consortium. The common template will facilitate partners in producing content to be included in the Newsletter. Email contacts will be selected from the database of stakeholders. A "**Join the project**" form, which will be soon accessible from P2Green website, will provide additional contacts to be included in the mailing list, especially from farmers and agriculture professionals.

Sendinblue – is the Software as A Service (SAAS) for relationship marketing ([link](#))-selected as the platform to design P2GreeN’s newsletter and host the mailing list. Sendinblue will provide useful monitoring tools to evaluate the performance of the mailing strategy.

All the information concerning the Newsletter will be managed in strict compliance with **the Data Management Plan**, that will be drawn up by WP7.

5.2 Offline Channels

P2GreeN’s offline communication will rely on four channels: press releases, scientific publications, events and clustering activities. To support offline activities, WP6 leaders will develop and share with the consortium a D&E+C kit.

5.2.1 P2GreeN D&E+C Kit

WP6 will share with all P2GreeN partners a communication and dissemination kit to support offline outreach activities. The kit will include P2GreeN branded presentations, leaflets, brochures, posters, and a roll-up (see D6.3). Partners will also access the press release template with the project logo, an appropriate page setting, fonts and colours that visually identify P2GreeN.

Specific content will be developed for media professionals. An informative sheet, together with infographics will provide a standard and accessible presentation of the project. The idea is to give the media all the context information to write about P2GreeN.

All the material will be available and distributed among partners to be used as an information library and promotional tool at outreach and networking events. A digital version of the kit will be shared with the project’s teams to allow the partners to print the material when needed.

The informative material produced during the project will be collected and published on the P2GreeN website in specific sections, where it will remain public for at least 2 years after the end of project.

Posters & roll-up	
Purpose	For informational and promotional purposes in events and clustering activities
Format	Printed material and in pdf format
Distribution	By partners. To be publicly exhibited at partner institutions and project event locations

Leaflets & Brochures	
Purpose	For informational and promotional purposes in events and clustering activities

Format	Printed material, pdf optimized for computer reading and desktop printing
Distribution	By partners and stakeholders. To be available at partner premises and event locations; sent by email and available for download from the project website

Press release template	
Purpose	To visually identify P2Green among media professionals
Format	Printed material (not recommended), browsable pdf optimised for computer reading and desktop printing
Distribution	PDF document uploaded on P2Green's MS Teams channel

Standardised presentation	
Purpose	To serve informational and dissemination purposes, partners can use this presentation to give a general overview of the P2Green project in conferences, workshops, and meetings
Format	PowerPoint
Distribution	PowerPoint document uploaded on P2Green's MS Teams channel

Media materials	
Purpose	Facilitating media professionals when reporting about the P2Green project
Format	Printed material (not recommended), browsable pdf optimised for computer reading and desktop printing
Distribution	By media contacts. To be circulated by email and available for download from project website

Table 4: Materials included in the D&E+C Kit

5.2.2 Press Releases

Press releases offer one of the most efficient and effective ways to disseminate information, particularly to the media and to other organisations.

P2Green press releases will be shared through the common press (i.e., newspapers), popular scientific press, as well as the **Cordis News Section** ([link](#)). Each release will be published with strategic timing, focusing on achieving significant milestones, activities, and the publication of Manuscripts from the project's partners. Emphasis will be given to information of relevance to the project. A press release related to the kick-

off meeting has already been produced and shared on the P2Green website, partner's portals, and the Cordis News Section.

Project press releases, drafted by WP6 or by other partners, will be produced in English. Partners are still welcome to provide a translation in their own native languages. Then, the PR will be shared with local media and press offices and other media selected by partners in coordination with the CIP and Moverim. Individual press releases from partners are welcome. However, the PR must be:

- drafted following the Press Release Template;
- sent to the P2Green communication team for approval.

5.2.3 Scientific publications

P2Green scientific results and technological innovations will be disseminated through **open-access publications** in high-ranking international journals. Publications will be mainly used to communicate with researchers and professionals involved in the scientific fields of P2Green.

As emerged from the Internal Survey, most researchers/partners estimate that the project will release from **1 to 3 overall scientific publications per year**, including joint publications/co-authorships with project partner. This prediction is perfectly in line with the estimated reach specified in the Grant Agreement: indeed, the consortium aims at publishing in year 1 & 2 : 2 overall publications from P2Green in year 3 & 4 : 1 publication per research organization.

As emerging from the internal survey, partners plan to publish their articles mainly in **journals concerning environmental sciences** (e.g., Frontiers in Environmental Sciences, Science of the Total Environment, Journal of Environmental Management, Science of Total Environment, Ecological Engineering) and environmental **law** (e.g., RECIEL, EJRR or TEL – environmental or similar law journals).

5.2.4 P2Green branded events and clustering activities

Throughout the project duration, P2Green will organise end-user consultations, clustering events and interdisciplinary workshops.

Clustering events will encourage synergies with ongoing relevant European and International projects. P2Green's WP6 entails the organisation of **clustering events** for stakeholders to enhance networking and discussion on key challenges addressed by P2Green and raise awareness about them. Partners involved in the Internal Survey have provided a preliminary list of projects related to P2Green's research topics (Table 5). P2Green is also one of the projects invited to be part of the EU's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI). The project is willing to organise clustering activities with the projects mentioned in Table 6 and the CCRI.

As mentioned before, WP6 and WP5 will work in synergy in Task 5.5: Develop synergies and collaboration with Horizon Europe clusters 1-5 and projects, cities & regions across the EU.

Type of project	Name	Description	URL
EU-Funded projects	<i>CITY LOOPS</i>	The CityLoops project brings together seven European cities to pilot a series of demonstration actions to close the loop of two of the most important waste streams in Europe: Construction and Demolition Waste, and Bio-waste. Their aim is to become circular cities in which no resource goes to waste, driving the transition to the circular economy.	link
	<i>CIRCULAR BIOCARBON</i>	Turning urban waste streams into added-value products. CIRCULAR BIOCARBON presents a first-of-a-kind flagship biorefinery designed to valorise the Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW) and Sewage Sludge (SS) into added-value products.	link
	<i>CHORIZO</i>	CHORIZO aims to improve the understanding of how social norms (rules or expectations that are socially enforced) influence behaviour related to FLW generation. To significantly accelerate progress towards zero food waste, CHORIZO aims to use this knowledge to increase the effectiveness of decision-making and engagement of food chain actors, in changing social norms towards zero food waste.	link
	<i>NOVAFERT</i>	In line with the Zero Pollution action plan, the “Farm to Fork” strategy and the new Fertilising Product Regulation, NOVAFERT will demonstrate the technical, economic, and environmental feasibility and safe use of a wide portfolio of at least 25 alternative fertilising products, containing recovered nutrients from all 6 different waste streams mentioned in the call, with the goal of facilitating the replacement of synthetic and mineral fertilisers.	link
	<i>AgroFossil Free</i>	The aim of the project is to create a framework under which critical stakeholders will cooperate to evaluate and promote currently available fossil-energy-free strategies and technologies (FEFTS) in EU agriculture to diminish in the short term and eliminate in the long run fossil	link

		fuels use in any farming process from cradle to farm gate, while maintaining yield and quality of the end-product.	
	<i>FoodCLIC</i>	The EU-funded FOODCLIC project will create more sustainable urban food environments by building strong science–policy–practice interfaces (i.e. food policy networks) and experimenting with innovative approaches and business models in Living Labs across eight European city-regions.	link
	<i>BOOST</i>	BOOST aims to boost agribusiness acceleration and digital hub networking by providing a sophisticated training program for the application of sustainable Precision Agriculture (PA) methodologies on management, agripreneurship, marketing, networking, and digital transformation delivered through an innovative educational and networking platform.	link
	<i>REWAISE</i>	REWAISE will create a new “smart water ecosystem”, mobilising all relevant stakeholders to make society embrace the true value of water, reducing freshwater and energy use, resulting in a carbon free, sustainable hydrological cycle, to transition into a resilient circular economy.	link
	<i>HYDROUSA</i>	HYDROUSA will provide innovative, regenerative and circular solutions for (1) nature-based water management of Mediterranean coastal areas, closing water loops; (2) nutrient management, boosting the agricultural and energy profile; and (3) local economies, based on circular value chains.	link
	<i>NEX-LABS</i>	NEX-LABS project aims to support the implementation of clean technologies for sustainable and resilient growth of agri-food sector production based on a more efficient use of energy (renewable/solar solutions) and water (wastewater treatment, water harvesting or reuse solutions) in Mediterranean Partner Countries region thanks to the contribution of information and telecommunication technology	link

		(ICT) such as blockchain technology, IoT, AI, Machine Learning and Big Data.	
	<i>REDOL</i>	The overall objective of REDOL is to advance the technological, managerial, economic, and social readiness level of EU Hubs for circularity by demonstrating innovative and sustainable routes to valorise solid urban waste (SUW) flows through Industrial and Urban symbiosis (I-US) approaches.	link
	<i>SYMSITES</i>	The SYMSITES project aims at developing new technologies and solutions based on the Industrial and Urban symbiosis (I-US) concept, for local and regional collaborations among diverse actors (Citizens, Municipalities and Entreprises) and sectors improving the sustainability of the use of industrial and societal resources starting from wastewater and waste materials.	link
	<i>BioRural</i>	BioRural seeks to promote currently available small-scale bio-based solutions with a view to strengthen Bioeconomy in European rural areas. To this purpose, BioRural has identified “success stories” (covering all Bioeconomy Themes) coming from all 4 geographic quartiles in Europe in which the BioRural consortium operates.	link
	<i>MainstreamBio</i>	The MainstreamBIO project will introduce small-scale bio-based solutions into mainstream practice across rural Europe, stimulating the participation of a wider range of rural actors in the development of the bioeconomy.	link
	<i>ACTIONr</i>	The ACTIONr project will unravel new tools and pathways to optimise nitrogen use efficiency (NUE), decelerate the N cycle and decrease the environmental footprint of reactive N (Nr).	link
	<i>CAFE</i>	The CAFE project will develop prospective scenarios for nutrient recovery and assess pathways towards circularity. The project will use complex networks and methods converting	link

		and analysing existing data sets to generate logistics networks relevant to these scenarios.	
	<i>H4C EUROPE</i>	The H4C Europe project will create a European Community of Practice (ECoP). It will provide a community, knowledge platform, and exchange structures that will help the existing and future hubs in creation, management, and growth, by overcoming barriers to IS/I-US/C.	link
	<i>Water Mining</i>	WATER-MINING is a research and innovation project that develops energy-efficient technologies for treating wastewater from urban and industrial areas and from desalination, whilst promoting the extraction of valuable products from the residues generated during the process.	link
CCRI PROJECTS	<i>Agro2Circular</i>	The Agro2Circular project will develop the first recycling value chain for post-industrial multilayer films based on a synergistic approach. It will combine innovative sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination and mechanical recycling.	link
	<i>HOOP</i>	The HOOP project will help to unlock urban circular bio-economy projects and deploy local bio economies in eight European cities and regions (known as Lighthouses (LH)) by providing Project Development Assistance (PDA) and tools to overcome their barriers.	link
	<i>InvestCEC</i>	InvestCEC will develop a replicable model for the implementation of circular economy projects in cities and regions across Europe, while considering all relevant stakeholders. Specifically, the model will address the city and region's needs, support entrepreneurs in making their circular economy solution investment ready and include the investment program set up and management. T	link
	<i>BIOMODEL4REGIONS</i>	The BIOMODEL4REGIONS project aims to support the establishment of innovative governance models at local and regional levels. BIOMODEL4REGIONS works to create	link

		better-informed decision-making processes, social engagement, and innovation to support and strengthen the European Union (EU) and international, scientific policy interfaces.	
	<i>CircularInvest</i>	CircularInvest is a CCRI-PDA initiative proposed by 4 organisations (META, INOVA+, Circle Economy and ICLEI EURO) that aims to provide project development assistance (PDA) to selected circular economy (CE) project promoters from across Europe so as to access the resources needed to develop significant CE investment projects at local and regional scale and to close the investments during the action.	link
	<i>ROBIN</i>	ROBIN aims to empower Europe’s regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.	link
	<i>DEFINITE-CCRI</i>	The DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a deal engine, providing technical, financial and circular economy expertise through local project development assistance in an unprecedented and streamlined process to cities, regions and project developers.	link
Other national or international projects	<i>RECAPTURE</i>	RECAPTURE has 3 short-term goals: 1) optimization of fertiliser formation to work with conventional farming equipment; 2) review the applicability of SPCR178 certification for urine and other emerging products; 3) conceptual idea of a tag-on to fertiliser certifications to include environmental aspects.	link
	<i>RUN</i>	The objective of the RUN project (Rural Urban Nutrient Partnership) is to close the nutrient cycle between urban and rural regions. RUN links the development of new and innovative technologies, the analysis of material flow models, systemic scenario analyses and social science/participative methods to accomplish this.	link

	<i>SUSKULT</i>	The SUSKULT joint project is working on an innovative, closed cycle agrosystem that overcomes current and future challenges. The goal is to develop and establish an innovative hydroponics-based food production system, in which plants grow and thrive within the framework of indoor cultivation using nutrient solutions. The “SUSKULT cropping system” obtains the required resources as well as heat and water directly from a wastewater treatment plant!	link
	<i>TWIST ++</i>	In this project, integrated and forward-looking technical solutions are to be found that intelligently combine disposal tasks for wastewater with supply tasks for drinking water and increase the flexibility of the overall system to adapt to future changes.	link
	<i>TANGO - W</i>	TANGO-W is an applied research project that uses the concept of Urban Transformative Capacities (UTC) to evaluate cities’ potential for sustainability, specifically at the intersection of food, energy, and water systems. By doing so, the project aims to help cities tackle challenges associated with climate change and encourage more sustainable urban development	Link
	<i>FoodSecure</i>	FoodSecure deals with global food security through better sanitation, exploring the potentials of urine recycling.	Link
	<i>ZirkulierBAR</i>	zirkulierBAR is building an innovative and scalable recycling facility for the recycling-oriented treatment of the contents of dry toilets. The end products are non-hazardous, nutrient-rich, and low-emission recycling fertilisers for agriculture and horticulture.	link
	<i>BONEX</i>	BONEX is a project funded by the PRIMA programme focused on providing practical adapted tools to facilitate the practical implementation of the WEFE nexus in the Mediterranean.	link

	<i>YES - Europe</i>	YES – Europe create a community of young people passionate about energy and sustainability and offer them a platform and resources to create their own initiatives and projects while gaining valuable skills. Organisation of Event and Knowledge Sharing.	link
	<i>Confcooperative UE</i>	Organise informative events and offer support for EU project to be implemented in Italy.	link

Table 5: Projects which could cluster with P2GreenN

WP6 will support WP4 through organising bilateral meetings with the aim to spread ideas, report about activities, and present the project’s recommendations to raise the target stakeholders’ awareness about the innovation potential of P2GreenN.

In general, WP6 will support the other WPs with the best D&E+C strategy for the workshops they will organise (see annex). WP6, together with WP3, WP4 and WP5 will contribute to M10 “Knowledge transfer to the follower regions to re-connect urban waste recovery with rural agri-food production in these areas”. The knowledge transfer will be done in workshops in the follower regions and their participation on P2GreenN events.

Annual exploitation workshops will be organised at a European level by CIP to help identify the key exploitable results of the project and explore potential policy changes. D6.7 and D6.8 will also provide detailed information on the 2 conferences that P2GreenN will organise with stakeholders.

5.2.5 P2GreenN participation in external events

To help promote awareness about the project and its results and boost the project's engagement, P2GreenN will participate in external events. These activities will increase P2GreenN’s impact and visibility and facilitate discussion with stakeholders sharing similar research interests and enhance exploitation.

Partners will be encouraged to participate in major international, national and regional conferences relevant to the project’s topics and disseminate project activities through oral presentations, posters, and discussions.

Partners involved in the Internal Survey plan to attend conferences and events to promote the P2GreenN project in the period 2023 - 2024. The Survey requested the partners to specify which conferences and events they planned to attend. The non-exhaustive list in Table 6 summarises the answers collected.

Event Title	Approx. Date	Location	URL
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Verde.Tec – Environmental Technologies	17-19 March 2023	Athens, Greece	link
Forward Green – adapting circular economy	31 March - 2 April 2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	link
International Conference on Environment and Life Science (EUCELS)	1 - 2 April 2023	Cologne, Germany	link
Global Water Intelligence Summit – GWS 2023	8 – 10 May 2023	Berlin, Germany	link
BlueTech Forum 2023	17 – 18 May 2023	Edinburgh, UK	link
Biennale Architettura 2023	20 May – 26 November 2023	Venice, Italy	link
Natural & Organic products Europe	16 – 17 April 2023	London, UK	link
Organic Food Conference 2023	22 – 23 May 2023	Sansepolcro, Italy	link
EU Green Week	3 – 11 June 2023	Brussels, Belgium	link
Re:publica	5 – 7 June 2023	Berlin, Germany	link
13th AEDyR International Congress	13 – 15 June 2023	Granada, Spain	link
Annual conference of RSA	14–17 June 2023	Ljubljana, Slovenia	link
European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW)	20 – 22 June 2023	Brussels, Belgium	link
3rd Global Conference on Agriculture	24 – 25 June 2023	Amsterdam, Netherlands	link
6th IWA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment	26 – 29 June 2023	Girona, Spain	link
AESOP (Association of European Schools of Planning) ANNUAL CONGRESS 2024	July tba	Paris, France	

European Wastewater Management Conference & Exhibition	4 – 5 July 2023	Manchester, UK	link
European Environmental Law Forum Conference 2023	31 August – 1 September 2023	Leipzig, Germany	link
Future for Food & Farming Summit	tba	tba	link
UACES 53rd Annual Conference	3-6 September 2023	Belfast, UK	link
The 10th International Conference On Agriculture 2023 - Theme: “Global Food Security: Stopping Crop Losses”	21 – 22 September 2023	Jakarta, Indonesia	link
18th Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment systems	24 – 29 September 2023	Dubrovnik, Croatia	link
International Conference “Closed cycles and the Circular Society 2023: The power of ecological engineering” of the International Ecological Engineering Society (IEES)	1 – 5 October 2023	Creta, Greece	link
Hungarian Regional Science Association (MRTT)	tbd	tbd	link
IDA Water Reuse & Recycling Conference 2023	10 – 11 October 2023	Seville, Spain	link
9th IWA-ASPIRE Conference and Exhibition 2023	22 – 26 October 2023	Kaohsiung, Taiwan	link
5th IWA Resource Recovery Conference	1 – 4 November 2023	Shenzhen, China	link
Aquatech Amsterdam 2023	6 – 9 November 2023	Amsterdam, Netherlands	link

ECOMONDO 2023	8 – 11 November 2023	Rimini, Italy	link
AGROTICA 2024	1 - 4 February 2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	link

Table 6: Key events to be attended by P2Green's partners

In the survey the partners were asked whether they plan to organise any conference or event to promote the P2Green project.

At the time of this deliverable, we have received confirmation of the following events

- Sanitation 360 will organize a Demo Day on the 14th of June
- Eco Village Hannover is planning Information days for members (850 members)
- Organisation of an event in 2023 or 2024 to talk about the Saint-Vincent-de-Paul experience and P2Green project.

Other events are to be organized in other tasks and other WPs as reported in the Grant Agreement in the section **Implementation 3.1. Work plan & resources** (see the list in Annex).

For the event **EU Green Week** scheduled from 3 to 11 June 2023 in Brussels, Belgium ([link](#)), P2Green applied for a Partner event during the conference. The event is titled “**P2Green: New circular governance solutions for the transition from fork to farm**” and it will be organised in a hybrid form on 07.06.2023 from 11:00 to 12:30 CET. During the event, there will be an in-depth discussion on skills/upskilling of regional actors and local authorities for implementing successful nutrient recovery systems. The activity is mainly addressed to policy makers, youth, media, scientists and researchers.

6. Evaluation

The evaluation strategy can be broken down into:

- Key performance Indicators (KPI) and Targets
- Reporting of D&E+C activities Dissemination Table

The evaluation strategy will be carried out continuously to monitor trends and identify where modifications and improvements need to be made regarding the utilisation of tools, channels, and platforms; the crafting of messages, the alignment of media and messaging with the target audiences, and timeliness.

6.1 KPI & Targets

KPIs are quantifiable goals that offer perspective on P2Green development. Measuring communication KPIs can identify the type of content, information, and knowledge our audience respond to best.

WP6 will monitor and measure dissemination KPIs, target numbers are shown in Table 7

Channel	Description	KPI	Estimated reach (targets)
Website	Design & Development of the project's brand identity & website	Website online	1
	Regular update of the website content	No. of unique page visits to the website	100 000
Social Media	LinkedIn	Likes/group members/posts	1000
	Facebook	Likes/posts/followers	500
	YouTube	Viewers	500
	Twitter	Tweets/retweets/followers	800
	Instagram	Likes/posts/followers	500
	Research Gate	Readers/citations	750
Clustering activities	The consortium will engage with other projects funded within the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) in different types of activities.	No. of engagements per year	3 (9 by the end of the project)
Journal publications	The consortium will seek to publish in high- impact journals. Partners will work with WP6 leaders and the scientific coordinator to proactively identify potential key publications.	No. of peer-reviewed publications per year	2 (6 in total)
Presentation at events	Presentations will engage a wide range of audiences and stakeholders about relevant topics.	No. of presentations per year	3 (9 in total)
Newsletter distribution	Regular (biannually) information is sent to participants, stakeholders, and partners.	No. of readers reached per issue	500
Blog post	Blogs will update stakeholders and the interested public with updates on project activities, resources and results while initiating discussions and dialogues.	No. of readers reached per publication	250

Table 7: Dissemination KPIs

6.1 Reporting of D&E+C activities

To facilitate the accurate monitoring and assessment of dissemination activities and to gauge and understand the impact of the actions performed, all P2GreenN partners will:

- prepare their activities following this Plan
- record their dissemination and communication activities
- report all P2GreenN specific dissemination activities for the periodic reports on the template that will be provided and stored on Teams for this purpose
- save evidence of the activities conducted

WP6 has developed a monitoring tool, the **DISSEMINATION TABLE**. This table must be filled in periodically throughout the project's lifetime, at least once a month, when relevant activities are organised. WP6 leaders will collect data and partners' inputs and produce aggregated tables. The monitoring tool consists of a set of template tables where details about the communication actions performed will be specified.

To summarise, WP6 will monitor and measure the indicators mentioned above by counting among the others:

Activity	KPI
P2GreenN's Events and Clustering activities	• N° of events participated in;
	• N° of events organised;
	• N° of participants in events;
External media	• N° of press releases produced and circulated;
	• N° of articles/appearances in press and media;
Web Portal	• N° of news published on the project website;
	• N° of downloads of documents from the project website;
Presence on social media	• N° of posts published on the project social networks;
Newsletters	• N° of messages sent to the project mail address.

Table 8: D&E+C Activity and KPIs summarised

Facebook, Twitter and Google Analytics allow to monitor the performance of P2GreenN's social networks and website and draft reports on it.

The DISSEMINATION TABLE will collect information from partners within 4 main spreadsheets:

Figure 9: Dissemination Table Dashboard

- Completed dissemination activities sheet

TYPE OF ACTIVITY* (select an option)	TITLE*	LINK*	DATE* (insert only the starting date)	TYPE OF AUDIENCE* (select an option)	SIZE OF AUDIENCE*	RELEVANCE TO P2Green (expected impact)	for conferences/workshops/events participation TITLE OF THE PAPER/PRESENTATION (if any)	Have you established CONTACTS WITH STAKEHOLDERS? If yes, WITH WHOM?	ADDITIONAL NOTES
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- List of scientific publications sheet

D. O. I.	TITLE	AUTHOR(S)	JOURNAL	PUBLISHER	PUBLISHER LOCATION	ISSN	ISSN	VOLUME/ISSUE	DATE OF PUBLICATION	EDITORS	BOOK TITLE	ISBN	URL	ONLINE SINCE	RELEVANT PAGES	OPEN ACCESS	PUBLICATION COSTS
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- IPR management sheet

TYPE OF IP RIGHTS (select an option)	APPLICATION REFERENCE (e.g. EP123456)	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION	SUBJECT OR TITLE OF APPLICATION	CONFIDENTIAL (select an option)	FORESEEN EMBARGO DATE	APPLICANT(S)	URL OF APPLICATION
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- Future dissemination activities sheet

TYP E O F A C T I V I T Y* (select an option)	TIT L E*	LI N K*	DA T E* (insert only the starting date)	TYPE O F A U D I E N C E* (select an option)	SIZE O F A U D I E N C E*	RE L E V A N C E T O P 2 G r e e N (expected impact)	A D D I T I O N A L N O T E S	T Y P E O F P A P E R (select an option)	T Y P E O F P R E S E N T A T I O N (select an option)	N A M E O F R E S P O N S I B L E A U T H O R	O T H E R P A R T N E R S I N V O L V E D	T I T L E O F T H E P A P E R	S T A T U S (select an option)
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A review of the impact of these activities will be carried out at crucial intervals and during reporting phases. The aim is to assess the effectiveness and timeliness of the activities. The conclusions will be used to inform and improve future actions, with recommendations for further activities.

7. Preliminary Exploitation Strategy

The here-reported D6.1 “Initial plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities” outlines a general strategy for the exploitation of the project’s results. However, a detailed exploitation strategy, including a description of concrete actions to establish a basis for exploitation activities and a Business Model Canvas, will be presented in **D6.2 “Final Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation at the end of the project”** (M 46) and **D 6.4 “Summary of exploitation workshops for knowledge transfer”** (M30).

All partners are called to dedicate time to exploit the project's results for policy impact, particularly ensuring the long-term sustainability of the project results and establishing an enduring legacy for the project. All partners will be involved in exploitation efforts, using their connections, well-known strengths in the field, and reputation.

7.1 Key Exploitable results

The project partners will report to the Management Board (MB) the most relevant results for knowledge transfer and commercial exploitation. However, in the project Grant Agreement, P2Green already identified some **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** relevant to the project exploitation. In addition, the technology-level assessment of KERs will be included in D 6.4. Moreover, D 6.2 will develop an overall detailed exploitation roadmap including the exploitation strategy of the involved partners based on the activities carried out in previous years of the project implementation. The roadmap will be able to support the attraction of different stakeholders at national and international levels. A summary of anticipated KERs is reported in Table 10 below.

WP	Key Exploitable Results (KERs)	IPR Owner(s)	Potential users	Potential exploitation
1	Development of blueprints from P2Green pilot regions	All	Farmers, authorities, researchers and civil society organisations (e.g. NGOs, associations, etc.).	Potential of replication in other sites
2	Methodologies and criteria for data collection in P2Green	All	Scientific communities	In-house expertise, replication of data for new R&D projects.
3	Toolbox for Social Acceptance	All	Civil society organisations (e.g. NGOs, associations, etc.), farmers and farmers' associations, municipalities	Internal use to increase societal acceptance within their networks
4	Development of a sustainable governance framework for N & P management and recovery in the P2Green pilot regions	All	Public Authorities, Policy makers at local, national and international level	Replication of the P2Green governance approach
5	P2Green Replication Platform and Replication Action Plans for Front Runner Regions	All	Public authorities, policy makers at local, national and international level, scientific communities	Replication of the P2Green project in other suitable areas
5	Regional Replication Action Plans	All	Public authorities, policy makers at local, national and international level, scientific communities	Exploitation of the simulation results / open-source data
5	Guide on how to initiate, manage and scale circular solutions (report & workshops)	All	Organisations considering to initiate or already taking part in a partnership within circular solutions	Exploitation for in-house expertise

Table 9 Summary of anticipated KERs

Exploitation will be categorised in **short-term** implementations within the project time span and the ideas will be discussed during the annual exploitation workshop (see 5.2.4 of this Deliverable) and reported in D6.4 (“Summary of exploitation workshops for knowledge transfer”). The short-term strategy will be accompanied by **medium-term** and **long-term activities** beyond the project. The annual exploitation workshops will help to find the additional key exploitable results in support to the WP 3 activities of identification of the key enabling drivers that exist in the new value chains compared to traditional value chains. Annual exploitation workshops also contribute to conducting a joint market analysis to identify the commercialisation potential for relevant consortium members and specify the required IP protection measures.

In the case of promising results, an assessment of market opportunities will be carried out in D 6.2. In this case, Steering Committee will decide with the innovators on the potential products for exploitation and establish a plan for patent application and further technology transfer steps. The exploitation of the innovations developed within the project will be carried out directly by the individual partners (e.g., for further research or commercial or industrial exploitation in their activities) or by others (other beneficiaries or third parties, e.g., through licensing or transfer of ownership of the results).

P2Green Steering Committee ensures that partners will make the most of all project results by providing their uptake by a maximum of concerned stakeholders mainly identified and involved in the project activities toward P2Green project partners and

organized events during and after the end of the project. P2GreeN will build a sustainable governance framework. Indeed, P2GreeN solutions will be valorised in the Policy brief (D6.7 and D6.8), particularly in synergy with other evidence produced by relevant project listed in Table 9 .

The policy briefs will always be proposed taking into account the potential barriers to exploiting P2GreeN's results. These barriers could include lack of adequate standards, lack of production capacities, issues related to local and international regulations, IP issues, unease with innovation, lack of funding, etc. All these aspects will be widely analysed within WP 5

7.2 Exploitation phases

P2GreeN's exploitation strategy defines a clear set of actions to foster the use of exploitable results, defined as any tangible or intangible output generated as a result of the project. As stated in the Grant Agreement, each beneficiary must take measures aiming to exploit its results, either in other research activities, outside the project activities, in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or, finally, in standardisation activities. The IPR strategy in place (D7.1) will describe the IPR protection forms that the consortium will use to protect its results.

To maximize its impact, P2GreeN will perform different exploitation activities, articulated into three phases (see Figure 12):

M1 – M23: Preliminary exploitation activities, identifying potentially interested stakeholders, the definition of the exploitation strategy and the planning of the exploitation activities. Task 5.1 will support the analysis of the potential market opportunities, especially for the Toolbox for Social acceptance (WP 3), the development of a sustainable governance framework for N & P management (WP 4); the innovation platform (WP 7) and blueprints form P2GreeN's pilot regions (WP 1). To foster the exploitation pathway of P2GreeN solutions, partners aim at preparing a project proposal for the call *Clean environment and zero pollution (HORIZON-CL6-2024-ZEROPOLLUTION-01)* proposing a project idea that could be the *Best available techniques to recover or recycle fertilising products from secondary raw materials (topic title)*.

M24 - M36: During the third year, the project will carry out market research for the potential commercialisation of the project outcomes, and will identify Interested industrial stakeholders. As in the project, there are 12 SMEs and 3 large-scale enterprises, of which one is a bank to cover the crucial aspect of financing innovative systems solutions for upscaling and mainstreaming. These partners are engaged to share with the consortium their preliminary market analysis and take advantage of their preliminary contacts with external stakeholdes to explore the market. Therefore, the project will organise meetings with potentially interested stakeholders (T4.2) to assess their needs and interests and build its business model.

M37 – M48: During the last year, partners will intensify contacts with regional, national and EU policy makers and industry stakeholders. 3 P2GreenN pilot regions, based in Gotland, the Metropolitan Region of Hamburg- Hannover and the La Axarquia region will already have established an innovation ecosystem for the systems transformation that the 4 P2GreenN follower regions, located in Italy, Greece, France and Hungary, will be able to adopt and scale up thereby reaching out to the key potential stakeholders to exploit the Regional replication actions plans (WP 5). D6.2 Final Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation at the end of the project will be produced in this period.

Figure 10: Exploitation Calendar

8. Conclusions and Outlook

This Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities describes the strategies for communicating, disseminating and exploiting P2GreenN activities and developments to ensure maximum and sustainable impact throughout and beyond the projects' lifespan. Adherence to and development of this integrated Plan will ensure that P2GreenN activities will be given maximum visibility by all partners as the project evolves and matures.

9. Annex

month	where	Number of events	what	notes	who's responsible?	size of audience/ number interviews
M1	Germany	1	Project meeting		AGR, IGZ	all project partners
M1	Germany	1	T4.2 Workshop for the consortium about stakeholder awareness	combined with the first project meeting	CBS	30
M6	each pilot regions	3 - one per pilot region	T4.2 3 pilot workshops for stakeholder awareness	Digital/ in-person TBD at KOM	CBS	20 per region
M6	each pilot regions		T3.3 focus groups interviews	combined with T4.2 3 pilot workshops for stakeholder awareness	IRS, IAAC, ENPC, SustC	min. 18 to 24 - 6 to 8 per region
M6	each pilot regions	3 - one per pilot region	T4.3 co-creation session about governance framework	combined with T.42 3 pilot workshops and T4.2 1 st sprint	ICLEI, CBS	min. 15 per region
M6	each pilot regions	3 - one per pilot region	T4.2 1st sprint of prototype development alongside pilot workshops	combined with T4.2 3 pilot workshops and T4.3 co-creation session	CBS	min. 15 per region
M8-9	each pilot regions		T3.3 semi-structured interviews	Based on the focus group, we would conduct semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders.	IRS	15 - min. 5 per region
M10-13	each pilot regions		T3.3 primary surveys	(The relatively wide time interval is due to the summer holiday season. This is the case if the project starts in September 2022.	IRS	150 - 50 per region
M11	Spain	1	Project meeting	combined with T6.3 1 st exploitation workshop, T1.4 in-person cross-fertilization Workshop, T3.1 in-depth interviews	AGR, IGZ	all project partners
M11	Spain	1	T1.4 cross-fertilization Workshop		BioA	15
M11	each pilot regions		T3.1 in-depth interviews		TRA	min. 9 – 3 per pilot region
M11	Spain	1	T6.3 1 st exploitation Workshop		CIP	25
M12	in person or online, TBD	4 - 1 per follower region	T5.3 focus groups		CERTH	25
M9-M12	TBD, face-to-face interviews (digital or in-person)		T5.2 meeting/interview for the definition of the current status of the replication site		IRIDRA	8 – 1 for each replication site

month	where	Number of events	what	notes	who's responsible?	size of audience/ number interviews
M17	Sweden	1	Project meeting	combined with T6.3 2 nd exploitation workshop	AGR, IGZ	all project partners
M17	Sweden	1	T6.3 2 nd exploitation workshop		CIP	50
M17	each pilot regions	3 - one per pilot region	T1.2 official field visits 2 nd year		BioA, SLU, EVH	20
M17	in person or online, TBD	3 - one per pilot region	T4.3 2nd round co-creation session		CBS, ICLEI	min. 15 per region
M18	each follower region	4 - one per follower region	T5.3 1st physical Workshop to inform local stakeholders		CERTH	20
M18	each follower region		T3.3 focus groups interviews	combined with T.5.3 1 st Physical workshops for stakeholder awareness	IRS	24 to 32 - 6 to 8 per focus group/ follower region
M 20-22	digital		T3.3 semi-structured interviews		IRS	16 (4 interviews for each follower region)
M23	Italy	1	Project meeting	combined with T6.3 2 nd exploitation workshop	AGR, IGZ	all project partners
M24	France	1	T4.1 Workshop in Paris with WP 4 + Paris for cross fertilization		ENPC	15
M24	TBD, in-person	1	T6.3 conference	combined with T5.3 1 st virtual workshop	MOV	100
M21-M24	TBD, face-to-face interviews (digital or in-person)		T5.2 meeting/interview for the discussion of the potential alternatives and the definition of the weights for the criteria evaluation		IRIDRA	8 – 1 for each replication site
M25	online	1	T5.3 1 st virtual workshop EU-wide		CERTH, TRA, ICLEI	50
M29	Greece	1	Project meeting	combined with T3.4 Interviews	AGR, IGZ	all project partners
M29	online		T3.4 Interviews		TRA	min. 9 – 3 per pilot region
M29	each pilot regions	3 - one per pilot region	T1.2 official field visits 3 rd year	combined with the T1.4 cross-fertilization workshop and the T4.2 2 nd sprint of prototype development	BioA, SLU, EVH	25
M29	online	1	T1.4 cross-fertilization Workshop		BioA	40

month	where	Number of events	what	notes	who's responsible?	size of audience, number interviews
M29	Germany	1	T6.3 3 rd exploitation workshop		CIP	50
M29	each pilot regions	3 - one per pilot region	T4.2 2 nd sprint prototype development		CBS	min. 15 per region
M32-34	each follower region		T3.3 primary surveys	50 people per follower region would be applied	IRS	200 - 50 per survey (1 for each follower region)
M34	digital	3 - one per pilot region	T4.3 training sessions to present governance framework		CBS, ICLEI	15
M35	Hungary	1	Project meeting		AGR, IGZ	all project partners
M35	digital	1	T3.3 presentation of the video games in a workshop	combined with the project meeting	IAAC	TBD
M36	each follower regions	4 - one per follower region	T5.3 2 nd Workshop		CERTH	20
M32-M36	TBD, face-to-face interviews (digital or in-person)		T5.2 meeting for the discussion of the multicriteria analysis results		IRIDRA	8 - 1 for each replication site
M36	TBD	1	T4.3 Event follower region workshop to transfer guidelines for governance	Digital	CBS, ICLEI	40
M38	online	1	T5.3 2 nd virtual workshop EU-wide	could combined with the T1.4 cross-fertilization workshop	CERTH, TRA, ICLEI	50
M38	online	1	T1.4 cross-fertilization Workshop		BioA	25
M42	France	1	Project meeting	combined with the T6.3 4 th exploitation workshop	AGR, IGZ	all project partners
M42	online	1	T6.3 4 th exploitation workshop	digital	CIP	50
M46	TBD, in-person	1	Final conference		MOV	100

Figure 11 : Overview about workshops, events and interviews planned by P2Green in a timely order. Synergies of events are shown and the size of audience and structure, project meetings are included.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No°**101081883**.